

THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH DISCONTINUOUS FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The effect of temperature on the ultimate tensile strength of composites reinforced with randomly oriented discontinuous fibers, is calculated for three failure modes. 1) If the interfacial bond is stronger than the matrix, the composite strength is maximized and follows the temperature dependence of the matrix. 2) If the perpendicular fibers delaminate, the strength is reduced but the temperature dependence is not affected. 3) Interfacial shear failure further reduces the strength, and the temperature dependence is no longer defined by the matrix. The calculated strengths are in good agreement with experimental results for metal and polymer composites.

INTRODUCTION

Metal or polymer composites appropriate for automotive applications are usually reinforced with discontinuous (chopped) fibers. The distribution of these fibers is determined by the processing conditions, but typically approximates a planar randomly oriented array. If a strong bond is attained at the fiber matrix interface, then the strength of the composite, in the plane of the fibers, may be considerably larger than that of the unreinforced material. In many applications, the effect of elevated temperature on the strength of the composite is of concern and the literature contains a variety of results. For some composites, the fibers provide no strengthening at room temperature but are very beneficial at elevated temperature, whereas in other composites strengthening is realized at both ambient and high temperature. In some cases the temperature dependence of the composite strength is similar to that of the unreinforced matrix strength, a strong indication that the failure is matrix controlled, but in other cases this is not so. This report provides a quantitative interpretation of these results based upon model calculations of the strength of composites with randomly oriented discontinuous fibers.

CALCULATION OF THE ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH

A simple method of calculating the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of a composite, reinforced with randomly oriented discontinuous fibers, was recently shown to be in good agreement with experimental values for metal matrix composites. The method is described in detail in earlier reports [1,2], so only an outline is given here. It is based upon the anisotropy of the strength $\sigma(\theta)$ of a composite with aligned continuous fibers, which is described by the Tsai-Hill equation [3]:

$$\sigma(\theta) = \left[\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{\sigma_L^2} + \left(\frac{1}{\tau^2} - \frac{1}{\sigma_L^2} \right) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{\sigma_T^2} \right]^{-1/2}, \quad (1)$$

where θ is the angle between the fibers and the direction of the applied load, σ_L is the strength when $\theta = 0^\circ$, σ_T is the strength when $\theta = 90^\circ$, and τ is the shear strength of the composite. This relationship is applied to a discontinuous fiber composite by recognizing that the strengthening provided by short fibers is less than that from long continuous fibers. According to the shear lag model of Kelly and Tyson [4], this occurs because a segment at each end of the fiber is not fully stressed. The matrix transmits the applied stress to the fibers by shear stresses developed at the interface, and a finite length ($\ell_c / 2$) at each end of the fiber is required for the stress in the fiber to reach a maximum. If this stress buildup is linear with distance, then the following well known equations [4] apply:

$$\sigma_L = V_f \sigma_f \left(1 - \frac{\ell_c}{2\ell} \right) + (1 - V_f) \sigma_m \quad \text{for } \ell \geq \ell_c$$

or

$$\sigma_L = V_f \sigma_f \frac{\ell}{2\ell_c} + (1 - V_f) \sigma_m \quad \text{for } \ell < \ell_c$$

where V_f is the volume fraction of the fiber, σ_f is the strength of the fiber, ℓ is the length of the fiber, σ_m is the strength of the matrix, and ℓ_c , the critical or ineffective length, is given by

$$\frac{\ell_c}{d} = \frac{\sigma_f}{2\tau_i} \quad (3)$$

where d is the fiber diameter, and τ_i is the shear strength of the interface. Thus the average isotropic strength provided by randomly oriented short fibers is obtained by substitution of equations (2) and (3) in equation (1) and integrating over all orientations. For a 2D planar random system,

$$\sigma_c = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sigma(\theta) d\theta. \quad (4)$$

This equation cannot be integrated in closed form, so advantage was taken of a computer to integrate it numerically.

A critical factor is the strength of the interfacial bond, since it controls the load transfer to the fibers (equation 3), the shear strength of the composite τ , and the stress (σ_i) required for delamination of the fiber/matrix interface. In this regard, important benchmarks are the tensile and shear strengths of the matrix (σ_m and τ_m). If the interfacial bond is weaker than the matrix, failure will occur at the interface. Conversely, if the interfacial bond is stronger than the matrix, failure will occur in the adjacent matrix and/or the fiber itself. In this study, it is assumed that the strength of the interfacial bond is independent of temperature, i.e. the interfacial chemistry is predetermined by the processing conditions. The following three scenarios are considered.

A) PERFECT BONDING, i.e. $\tau_i \geq \tau_m$ AND $\sigma_i \geq \sigma_m$.

This condition will yield the maximum attainable value of composite strength (σ_A). The value of τ_i (equation 3) will be effectively limited by, and will be equal to, the shear strength of the matrix (τ_m). Also under this condition, the shear strength of the composite (τ) is controlled by shear of the matrix and is approximately independent of the fiber volume fraction [5]. Thus, we can write:

$$\tau = \tau_i = \tau_m. \quad (5)$$

For aluminum alloys, τ_m is typically $0.67 \sigma_m$ [6]. For polymers, the von Mises' criterion was applied, i.e. $\tau_m = 0.58 \sigma_m$ [7]. Similarly, the maximum value of the transverse strength (σ_T) will be the tensile strength of the matrix:

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_m \quad (6)$$

The failure mode in this case will be a combination of fiber and matrix failure.

B) DELAMINATION, i.e. $\sigma_i < \sigma_m$ AND $\tau_i \geq \tau_m$

For randomly oriented fibers, the assumption of a strong interfacial bond is most likely to break down for the fibers oriented perpendicularly to the stress. If delamination occurs at a stress $\sigma_i < \sigma_m$, then equation (6) no longer applies. In fact, when such delamination occurs in an aligned composite, the transverse strength can be approximated by representing each fiber as a cylindrical hole in the matrix [8], i.e.

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_m \left[1 - 2(V_f / \pi)^{1/2} \right]. \quad (7)$$

Substitution of this expression in lieu of equation (6) (equation (5) still applies) yields a lower value of the composite strength (σ_B). The fracture surface in this case will exhibit grooves where fibers in the plane of fracture have delaminated.

C) DELAMINATION AND INTERFACIAL SHEAR, i.e. $\sigma_i < \sigma_m$ AND $\tau_i < \tau_m$

In this case the perpendicular fibers again delaminate so that equation (7) still applies. In addition, interfacial shear failure occurs at fibers with other orientations, appearing first for fibers at $\theta = 45^\circ$, where the applied shear stress is a maximum. The values of τ_i and τ will both be smaller than τ_m . In the examples considered in the next section, the value assigned to τ has a major influence on the composite strength. On the other hand, the value of τ_i is not critical because the fiber aspect ratio is substantially larger than the critical value (equation 3). So for simplicity, we set $\tau_i = \tau$ without incurring a significant error in the value of composite strength σ_C . The fracture surface in this case, will exhibit more extensive fiber pullout than in cases (A) and (B).

COMPARISON OF THEORY WITH LITERATURE DATA

1. SAFFIL/6061 ALUMINUM

Dinwoodie et al [9] have studied composites of Saffil fiber reinforced 6061 aluminum produced by either squeeze casting or powder metallurgy techniques. Their measurements of the tensile strength (Fig. 1) revealed differences between billets, thought to be associated with variations in fiber distribution. For the present purpose, the stronger billet is of particular interest. The dashed line in Fig. 1 corresponds to the strength of the non-reinforced alloy [9], which is here assumed to represent the strength of the matrix in the composite. Then for the Saffil fiber properties of $\sigma_f = 2$ GPa, $v_f = 0.29$ and $\ell / d = 30$, the calculated values of σ_A and σ_B are shown by the solid curves in Fig. 1. Clearly the higher strength composite is in excellent agreement with σ_A throughout the temperature range investigated.

2. GLASS/POLYPHENYLENE OXIDE

Trachte and Debenedetto [10] produced composites of polyphenylene oxide (PPO) reinforced with randomly oriented E-glass fibers by compression molding. Two types of composite were produced, namely with and without silane treatment of the fibers; the former were substantially stronger than the latter (Fig. 2). This difference was attributed to silane enhanced adhesion at the fiber-matrix interface, as was confirmed by scanning electron fractography. The bottom set of data in Fig. 2 shows the strength of the unreinforced PPO. If this is assumed to represent the strength of the matrix in the composites, then for the E-glass fiber properties of $\sigma_f = 3$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.2$ and $\ell/d = 300$, the values of σ_A and σ_B are as shown by the solid lines in Fig. 2. From the excellent agreement with the experimental values, we conclude that the adhesion promoted by silane produced a bond strength larger than the matrix strength even at -50°C i.e. $\sigma_i > 150$ MPa. With no silane treatment the bond strength is less than the matrix strength even at 180°C , i.e. $\sigma_i < 60$ MPa.

3. SAFFIL/ALUMINUM 4ZN 2MG

The tensile strength of a squeeze cast aluminum 4Zn 2Mg alloy with and without Saffil fibers was measured as a function of temperature by Friend [11]. His results are reproduced in Fig. 3. At high temperature the composite is substantially stronger than the unreinforced alloy, but at room temperature the strengths are essentially the same. This behavior has also been reported by other investigators [12,13] and seems quite typical of Saffil reinforced aluminum alloys. Also shown in Fig. 3 are the values of σ_A and σ_B based upon the Saffil fiber properties of $\sigma_f = 2$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.25$ and $\ell/d = 30$. The data points at 20°C and 120°C correspond very closely to σ_B , so we conclude that in this low temperature range the perpendicularly oriented fibers delaminated, i.e. $\sigma_i < \sigma_m$. On the other hand, the data points at 200°C and 300°C correspond to σ_A so we conclude that at these higher temperatures $\sigma_i > \sigma_m$. Thus as the matrix becomes weaker with increasing temperature, there is a transition in behavior which permits bounds to be placed upon the stress required for delamination, i.e. $160 \text{ MPa} < \sigma_i < 230 \text{ MPa}$.

4. GRAPHITE/POLYPHENYLENE OXIDE

Some of the PPO composites compression-molded by Trachte and Dibenedetto [10] were reinforced with Thornel graphite fibers ($\sigma_f = 1.4$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.25$ and $\ell/d = 450$), producing the tensile strengths shown in Fig. 4. At low temperatures the composite was weaker than the unreinforced PPO, at $\sim 0^\circ\text{C}$ the strengths were equal, but at high temperature substantial strengthening was achieved. Also shown in Fig. 4 are the calculated composite strengths for the three failure modes. The values of σ_C were obtained by assigning $\tau = 30$ MPa at temperatures $\leq 125^\circ\text{C}$. At higher temperatures this value of τ does not apply because it would be larger than the shear strength of the PPO. Thus the calculated curve which matches the experimental results involves a transition in fracture mode at 125°C . At temperatures $> 125^\circ\text{C}$, the perpendicularly oriented fibers delaminate, but the bond is strong enough to prevent interfacial shear failure. But at $T < 125^\circ\text{C}$, the shear strength of the PPO matrix is larger so that interfacial shear failure also occurs. This interpretation is consistent with the observations of Trachte and Dibenedetto [10] that for these composites "the primary mode of failure . . . was through fiber pullout, after interfacial debonding."

5. SAFFIL/ZINC 32AL

Lo, et al [14] have recently evaluated the effect of Saffil fiber reinforcement on the tensile strength of a squeeze cast zinc-32Al alloy. Their results are plotted in Fig. 5 and compared with the calculated composite strengths for the three failure modes, i.e. σ_A , σ_B and σ_C . The values of σ_C are for $\tau = 145$ MPa so they apply only for temperatures $\leq 130^\circ\text{C}$. (At higher temperatures

this value of τ is larger than the shear strength of the matrix alloy.) Thus excellent agreement with the experimental data is obtained on the basis of a model with poor interfacial bonding and a transition in fracture mode at 130°C. At temperatures higher than 130°C, the perpendicular fibers delaminate but the bond is strong enough so that shear occurs in the matrix rather than the interface (mode B). At $T < 130^\circ\text{C}$ the matrix is stronger so that interfacial shear failure occurs in addition to delamination (mode C). This interpretation is consistent with the electron microscopic observations of Lo et al [14] who concluded that "the dominant fracture mode in the composite materials was fiber/matrix decohesion."

SUMMARY

These calculations of the tensile strength of composites, reinforced with randomly oriented short fibers, are in good agreement with a variety of experimental results. It is shown that the effect of temperature on the tensile strength depends upon the strength of the interfacial bond, i.e the mode of failure. Three failure modes are considered.

- A) If the interfacial bond is stronger than the matrix ($\sigma_i > \sigma_m$ and $\tau_i > \tau_m$), the composite strength is optimized and the temperature dependence is similar to that of the matrix. Two examples are silane treated glass/ PPO (Fig. 2) and Saffil/6061 aluminum (Fig. 1).
- B) If the perpendicular fibers delaminate ($\sigma_i < \sigma_m$, $\tau_i > \tau_m$), the composite strength is reduced but still follows the temperature dependence of the matrix. A good example of this mode of failure is untreated glass/PPO (Fig. 2).
- C) If interfacial shear failure also occurs ($\sigma_i < \sigma_m$, $\tau_i < \tau_m$), the composite strength is reduced further and the temperature dependence no longer follows that of the matrix. This is well illustrated by graphite/PPO at temperatures less than 100°C (Fig. 4).

For some composites the available data appear to encompass a temperature range wherein there is a transition in failure mode. This occurs at the temperature where the matrix strength is equal to that of the interfacial bond (i.e. $\tau_i = \tau_m$ or $\sigma_i = \sigma_m$). For example, our calculations indicate that interfacial shear failure occurs at low temperatures in graphite/polyphenylene oxide but not at temperatures $> 125^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 4). Similarly, this transition from σ_C to σ_B with increasing temperature is apparent in the results for Saffil/Zn-32Al (Fig. 5). For Saffil/aluminum composites it is often observed that strengthening is achieved at high temperatures but not at room temperature [11-13]. According to our model this is due to a change in fracture mode from delamination (σ_B) at room temperature to perfect bonding (σ_A) at high temperature (e.g., Fig. 3). More detailed studies of these systems would be of interest to validate this interpretation.

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Figure 1. Effect of temperature on the tensile strength of 6061 aluminum reinforced with 0.29 v_f Saffil fibers. Experimental data from Dinwoodie et al [9]. Solid curves show calculated values of σ_A and σ_B .

Figure 2. Effect of temperature on the tensile strength of PPO without and with $v_f = 0.2$ glass fibers. Data from Trachte and Dibenedetto [10]. The strengths provided by silane treated and untreated fibers corresponds to σ_A and σ_B , respectively.

Figure 3. Effect of temperature on the tensile strength of an aluminum alloy without and with 0.25 v_f Saffil fibers. Experimental data from Friend [11]. Solid lines show calculated values of σ_A and σ_B .

Figure 4. Effect of temperature on the tensile strength of polyphenylene oxide without and with $v_f = 0.2$ graphite fiber reinforcement. Experimental data from Trachte and Dibenedetto [10]. Solid lines show calculated values of σ_A , σ_B and σ_C .

Figure 5. Effect of temperature on the tensile strength of a zinc - 32 wt.% Al alloy without and with $v_f = 0.24$ Saffil fiber reinforcement. Experimental data from Lo et al [14]. Solid curves correspond to calculated values of σ_A , σ_B and σ_C .